

Explainable AI (XAI) for AI-Acceptability: The Coming Age of Digital Management 5.0

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Abstract— This paper delves into the nascent paradigm of Explainable AI (XAI) and its pivotal role in enhancing the acceptability of growing AI systems that are shaping the Digital Management 5.0 era. XAI holds significant promise, promoting compliance with legal and ethical standards and offering transparent decision-making tools. The imperative of interpretable AI systems to counter the black box effect and adhere to data protection laws like GDPR is highlighted. This paper aims to achieve a dual objective. Firstly, it provides an in-depth understanding of the emerging XAI paradigm, helping practitioners and academics project their future research trajectories. Secondly, it proposes a new taxonomy of XAI models with potential applications that could facilitate AI acceptability. Although the academic literature reflects a crucial lack of exploration into the full potential of XAI, existing models remain mainly theoretical and lack practical applications. By bridging the gap between abstract models and the pragmatic implementation of XAI in management, this paper breaks new ground by launching the scientific foundations of XAI in the upcoming era of Digital Management 5.0.

Keywords— AI-acceptability, AI-reluctance, Explainable AI, XAI, human-AI collaboration, Digital Management 5.0.

I. INTRODUCTION

Naturally, human beings need to understand the origin of a system's results. This understanding enables individuals to assess the validity of the results and underlying processes [1]. That forms the basis of concerns expressed in many studies about the socio-organizational challenges arising from automation and autonomy within traditional AI systems. These systems cannot explain their decisions and processing mechanisms [2]. McKinsey's global survey [3] highlighted the surge in investment in AI, but its practical implementation faces obstacles due to socio-organizational factors, including resistance to AI-induced change. These challenges have contributed to a reluctance to adopt AI, impeding its integration within organizations [4].

The acceptability of technologies within organizations, including AI, is a research topic in managing Information Systems (MIS) [5]. Studies in this field mainly encompass socio-behavioral and socio-organizational aspects such as human-AI interactions, ethics, regulations, human-centered behavior, and business-IT alignment [6].

Our published research on AI acceptability [7] and [8] emphasizes that explicability is essential for accepting AI

systems in organizations. Given AI's inductive and black-box nature, implicit execution and the interpretation of results generate reluctance and trust issues [9].

Since the publication in 2018 of his acclaimed book "*The Book of Why*," Judea Pearl, the distinguished Turing Award winner, has emphasized the central role of interpreted causality in shaping the future of AI, realizing explicability [12], that catalyzed the Explainable AI (XAI) revolution [9]. In parallel, the 2018 French parliamentary report Villani, led by eminent mathematician *Cédric Villani* [13], focused on the explicability of AI systems. The EU's GDPR has further reinforced this need by introducing the "*right to explanation*" [14]. In addition, managers and users, hampered by prejudice, the AI black box, and customer skepticism, are under increasing pressure to adopt more transparent AI models [15].

The academic literature in economics and management reflects a growing interest in conducting research trials, as evidenced by recent proposals [17]. Nevertheless, many of these models remain theoretical and lack a socio-techno-pragmatic interpretation. That hampers their ability to solve explicability problems and demonstrate greater acceptability of AI.

Beyond the goal of XAI acceptability, our paper aims to raise awareness among researchers and management practitioners of the potential opportunities and challenges of XAI. As a pioneering work on this emerging topic, it contributes to the global discourse on XAI.

The paper comprises three main sections. The first section sets the context, addressing AI reluctance, AI acceptability, and the importance of explainable AI in the Digital Management 5.0 paradigm. The second section details our contribution and proposed research avenues for AI X's acceptability in management. The third and final section offers a discussion and outlines prospects.

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